

EFFECT OF PLY THICKNESS ON IMPACT DAMAGE MODES OF THIN-PLY CFRP LAMINATES

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Keywords: CFRP laminates, Thin-ply prepreg, Damage mode, CAI strength

ABSTRACT

In this study, impact tests and compressive after impact (CAI) tests of quasi-isotropic laminates, which had different ply thicknesses using thin-ply prepreg whose thickness was 0.02 mm, were conducted. The effects of ply thickness and impact energy on the damage modes in impact tests and CAI strength were investigated. Furthermore, a precise observation of failure by an impact load inside the laminates using X-ray computed tomography (X-ray CT) was carried out. Results confirmed that fiber breakages became a predominant damage mode by decreasing the ply thickness owing to constraining effect of neighbouring layers, while most of failures in thick-ply laminates were dominated by matrix damage such as matrix cracks and delamination. Moreover, when the ply thickness decreased, the decreasing rate of CAI strength became larger than that of thick-ply laminates owing to the accumulation of fiber breakage in thickness direction in the case of a high impact energy, while the CAI strength was improved when the impact energy was below 5 J/mm.

1 INTRODUCTION

In aerospace and automotive fields, research and development of structural materials using carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been promoted. For the application of CFRP for structural materials, it is necessary to evaluate their mechanical properties under a static load as well as a dynamic load which includes an impact load as an important design concern. It is essential to understand the mechanism of the damage mode caused by impact load because most of damages in CFRP caused by impact loads occur inside the laminate, such as delamination and matrix crack. However, it is difficult to detect these damages by visual inspection, and furthermore they cause a remarkable decrease in mechanical properties.

Recently, thin-ply prepreps (less than 0.1mm in thickness), which have an extremely low aerial fiber weight produced by using a fiber tow spreading technology, have attracted a significant attention [1]. There are lots of studies indicating that the first ply failure such as transverse cracks and delamination is suppressed and various mechanical properties of CFRP are improved by use of thin-ply prepreps [2-7]. The suppression effect of the first ply failure has been also confirmed by decreasing the ply thickness in impact tests.

Saito et al. [8] performed impact tests of quasi-isotropic laminates which consisted of thin-ply prepreps (0.04 mm in thickness) and standard ply prepreps (0.15 mm in thickness), respectively, in order to investigate the effect of ply thickness on damage modes during an impact event. They demonstrated that matrix cracks were suppressed and the location of delamination in thickness direction was localized near the mid-plane of the laminates, and that the CAI strength was improved by decreasing ply thickness. They also studied the mechanism for suppression of delaminations in thickness direction in thin-ply laminates, and showed that energy release rate by the propagation of matrix cracks was reduced when the ply thickness was decreased, using calculations with a FEM model.

It was also shown that the suppressing effect of ply failure such as matrix cracks and delamination during an impact event was increased by combining the decreasing of the ply thickness and the toughening of the interlaminar layer consisting of the resin layer containing particles of thermoplastic resin. However, a comprehensive understanding of the effect of ply thickness on mechanical properties after impact has not been established. Cugnoni et al. [9] studied the effect of ply thickness, toughening the matrix resin and interlaminar layer on CAI strength using quasi-isotropic laminates with ply thicknesses between 0.03 and 0.3 mm. Their results indicated that CAI strength was improved by each method and the effect was enhanced by combining these methods.

On the other hand, Garcia-Rodriguez et al. [10] conducted the quasi-static indentation (QSI) tests and impact tests of laminates manufactured with thin or standard-ply non-crimp fabrics (fiber aerial weight of 67 and 134 gsm per ply) and observed specimens after the load by X-ray CT in order to evaluate the difference of damage mode between the laminates. They demonstrated experimentally that the decrease in the stiffness of laminates was attenuated by suppressing matrix cracks and delamination while more fiber breakages occurred when the ply thickness was decreased, and then the maximum load during impact tests and the CAI strength of thin-ply laminates exhibited the lower values than those of standard-ply laminates. These previous studies showed an opposite tendency in terms of the effect of ply thickness on CAI strength, confirming that CAI strength was improved by toughening of interlaminar layer.

In this study, impact tests and CAI tests varying the impact energies were conducted using quasi-isotropic laminates which had different ply thickness (0.02, 0.12, 0.24 mm) that consisted of thin-ply prepreg sheet whose thickness was 0.02 mm. Then the advantage in mechanical properties of thin-ply materials except for a positive effect of interlaminar toughening was verified and the effect of ply thickness and impact energy on damage mode during an impact event was evaluated. Furthermore, a precise observation of the specimens after the impact using X-ray CT was conducted in order to investigate the effect of ply thickness on damage mode, especially the location of matrix cracks and delamination in thickness direction.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials

Quasi-isotropic laminates were fabricated using thin-ply prepregs which consisted of carbon fibers and epoxy resin. Table 1 shows the stacking sequence, ply thickness, plate thickness and fiber volume fraction of quasi-isotropic laminates used in this study. The material system used in this study was TR50S (Mitsubishi Chemical co., ltd) / epoxy resin (jER828: jER1001 = 4: 6, Mitsubishi Chemical Co., Ltd). The thin-ply prepreg sheet which was 0.02 mm in thickness made by using a fiber tow spreading technology originally developed in Industrial Technology Center of Fukui Prefecture. Table 2 indicates tensile and compressive properties of uni-directional laminates using thin-ply prepregs.

Quasi-isotropic laminates which had different ply thicknesses (0.02, 0.12, 0.24 mm) while keeping the same plate thickness (4.3 mm) were made by changing the number of prepreg sheets in the same direction. Fig. 1 shows the cross-sectional image of the laminates. The stacking sequences of the laminates were $[45/0/-45/90]_{24s}$ for “Thin” laminates, $[45_6/0_6/-45_6/90_6]_{4s}$ for “Intermediate” laminates, and $[45_{12}/0_{12}/-45_{12}/90_{12}]_{2s}$ for “Thick” laminates”, respectively. Laminates were prepared by hand lay-up and molded by an autoclave (130 °C, 0.5 MPa, 120 min) and no voids in laminates were detected by ultrasonic inspection (Insight Co., ltd). Specimens for impact tests according to ASTM D 7136M (150 mm in length and 100 mm in width) were cut out from the laminates.

2.2 Impact tests and CAI tests

In reference to ASTM D 7136M, impact tests of quasi-isotropic laminates with varying impact energies (3, 5, 7 J/mm) by adjusting the height of the impactor were conducted by using a weight-drop-type impact machine (IM1C-15, IMATK Co., Ltd, Fig. 2). The anti-rebound system was used so that the impact energy was loaded by only one impact. The weight of a hemispherical impactor of 16 mm in diameter was 5 kg. Specimens were attached to a steel support base containing a rectangular hole of 132 mm in length and 76 mm in width and impactor was dropped on the center of specimens.

Table 1: Stacking sequence of the quasi-isotropic laminates.

Code	Stacking sequence	Ply thickness [mm]	Plate thickness [mm]	V_f [%]
Thin	$[45/0/-45/90]_{24S}$	0.02	4.37	50.3
Intermediate	$[45_6/0_6/-45_6/90_6]_{4S}$	0.12	4.39	50.1
Thick	$[45_{12}/0_{12}/-45_{12}/90_{12}]_{2S}$	0.24	4.32	50.9

Table 2: Mechanical properties of uni-directional laminates.

Property	Unit	V_f^*	Relevant standard
Tensile modulus (0°) E_L	119 [GPa]	51.6	ASTM D 3039 M
Tensile modulus (90°) E_T	9.5 [GPa]	51.1	ASTM D 3039 M
Tensile modulus (45°) E_{45}	10.2 [GPa]	51.6	ASTM D 3039 M
Poisson's ratio ν_{LT}	0.32		ASTM D 3039 M
Ultimate tensile strength (0°) F_{Lt}	2333 [MPa]	51.6	ASTM D 3039 M
Ultimate tensile strength (90°) F_{Tt}	62 [MPa]	51.1	ASTM D 3039 M
Ultimate compressive strength (0°) F_{Lc}	985 [MPa]	51.1	JIS K 7076

* Fiber volume fraction of each laminate used for each test.

Figure 1: Cross-sectional images of (a) Thin laminates, (b) Intermediate laminates and (c) Thick laminates. The chain line indicates the mid-plane of the laminates.

Loads to specimens were measured by the load cell attached to the impactor and impact energies were calculated from impact speed measured by an optical sensor. The total energy was calculated by integrating the area under the load-displacement curves; the elastic energy was calculated by the area under the unloading curve; and the dissipated energy was obtained by subtracting the elastic energy from the total energy. Damage inside the specimens after impact were inspected by using ultrasonic inspection and X-ray CT (X radiia XRM-410 Versa, ZEISS Co., Ltd). The whole of specimens and their center region including the impacted point ($35 \text{ mm} \times 35 \text{ mm}$) were observed by ultrasonic inspection (1500×1000 pixel) and X-ray CT (scanning parameter: 40 kV, 200 μA , exposure time: 3 sec., pixel size: 35 μm), respectively. Fig. 3 shows the location of X-ray observation. The depth of dents at impact points were measured by a depth gage (DMD-210S, Teclock Co., Ltd). CAI tests and compressive tests of specimens without an impact load were conducted in reference to ASTM D 7137M and JIS K7076, respectively.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effects of ply thickness on failure mode

Table 3 depicts the results of impact tests and CAI tests, including the maximum load, maximum displacement, dissipated energy, projected delamination area, depth of dent and CAI strength. Figs. 4-

Figure 2: Pictures of impact test machine:
 (a) Overview of the machine and (b) Impactor and impact support fixture.

Figure 3: Location of X-ray CT observation.
 Rectangular line indicates the observed region ($35 \times 35 \text{ mm}^2$).

6 indicate photographs and ultrasonic inspection images of Thin, Thick and Intermediate laminates after impact tests, respectively. In each figure, upper images show pictures of the specimens from back face (opposite side of the impact side) and lower images were obtained from impact side by ultrasonic inspection. Right and lower images of ultrasonic inspection show projected images of failure from each side of specimens, respectively.

Thin laminates

Fig. 4 shows meandering cracks not along the fiber direction including fiber breakages occurred in the back face and cracks propagated with increasing an impact energy. Ultrasonic inspection revealed that an extremely large delamination occurred near the mid-plane and the size of delamination became larger with increase of the impact energies. The shapes of delaminations of Thin laminates were circular or of an ellipse, the end of which located in the center of specimen and the length of delamination in width-direction of the specimen became larger with increase of the impact energy.

Thick laminates

Fig. 5 indicates a matrix crack along the fiber direction occurred at the back face and the length of the crack became larger with the increase of the impact energy. Although the shape of delamination at 3 J/mm was circular, the delamination propagated to width direction at more than 5 J/mm. The fact that the direction of side line of a delamination corresponded to the fiber direction in each layer and the area of delamination became larger with the increase of the crack length indicated that delamination was induced by matrix cracks in each layer. Cross-sectional images show that distributed delaminations occurred in all interlaminar layers in thickness direction.

Intermediate laminates

Fig. 6 shows that both of matrix crack along the fiber direction and fiber breakages were observed at the back face in Intermediate laminates. Furthermore, the fact that distributed delaminations in thickness direction were observed similarly to Thick laminates while the projected damage area of

Table 3: Results of impact tests and CAI tests.

Thin laminates						
Impact energy [J/mm]	Maximum displacement [mm]	Maximum load [kN]	Dissipated energy [J/mm]	Projected damage area [mm ²]	Dent depth [mm]	CAI strength [MPa]
3	3.1	8.0	1.6	2449	0.11	283
5	4.8	8.3	3.5	3178	0.23	217
7	7.0	8.4	4.5	3495	0.80	155
Intermediate laminates						
Impact energy [J/mm]	Maximum displacement [mm]	Maximum load [kN]	Dissipated energy [J/mm]	Projected damage area [mm ²]	Dent depth [mm]	CAI strength [MPa]
3	3.2	7.8	1.4	1510	0.08	271
5	4.6	9.0	2.5	2719	0.12	211
7	5.2	11.5	3.5	3750	0.14	183
Thick laminates						
Impact energy [J/mm]	Maximum displacement [mm]	Maximum load [kN]	Dissipated energy [J/mm]	Projected damage area [mm ²]	Dent depth [mm]	CAI strength [MPa]
3	3.5	7.8	1.4	817	0.10	236
5	4.7	9.0	2.5	1497	0.17	188
7	5.8	10.1	5.0	2080	0.47	161

Intermediate laminates was the same as Thin laminates, indicates that Intermediate laminates exhibited an intermediate damage mode between Thin and Thick laminates. These results showed that ply thickness has a large influence on damage mode including the size and the location in thickness direction of delamination, fiber breakage.

Concerning the depth of dents, Thin laminates exhibited the largest value when impact energy was 7 J/mm while there was no difference in any laminates below 5 J/mm. The appearance of the deep dent in 7 J/mm indicates that the failure including the fiber breakage occurred even at the impact side in the case of a high impact energy. Comparing the maximum load, Intermediate and Thick laminates showed the larger value than Thin laminates when the impact energy was more than 5 J/mm. This tendency was also confirmed in Ref. [10] by Garcia-Rodriguez which explained that these results were attributed to the reduction of stiffness of the laminates caused by the accumulation of fiber breakages in thickness direction.

3.2 Damage mode observation by X-ray CT

A precise observation of each laminate after impact (5 J/mm) was conducted using X-ray CT in order to investigate the damage inside the laminates. Figs. 7-9 show the results of the observation of Thin, Thick and Intermediate laminates, respectively.

Thin laminates

Fig. 7 indicates that the locations of delaminations in thickness direction were localized near the mid-plane and on the tensile side in Thin laminates. Besides, a crack perforating into various layers was observed near the back face. The fact that the length of this crack was more than 1 mm indicates that this crack is mainly associated with fiber breakages. The images near the mid-plane shows a large delamination propagated with matrix cracks induced by fiber breakages.

A large delamination occurred near the mid-plane was caused by the out-of-plane shear stress that reached the maximum at the mid-plane of laminates. Focusing on the location of delamination in thickness direction in Thin laminates (Fig. 4), it was confirmed that the location shifted to the

Figure 4: Pictures and ultrasonic inspection images of Thin laminates.

Figure 5: Pictures and ultrasonic inspection images of Thick laminates.

Figure 6: Pictures and ultrasonic inspection images of Intermediate laminates.

compressive side with increase of the impact energy. These results were attributed to the fact that the propagation of fiber breakages in thickness direction became larger and the ratio of the intact part which could bear the load was decreased from the back side of the laminates, when the impact energy was high. These results indicate that a large delamination near the mid-plane was triggered by the propagation of fiber breakages from the back face.

Figure 7: Images of Thin laminates by X-ray CT:
 (a) Cross-sectional image (0° direction), (b) Cross-sectional image (90° direction)
 and (c) Images of representative interlaminar layers indicated by arrow in (a).

Figure 8: Images of Thick laminates by X-ray CT:
 (a) Cross-sectional image (0° direction), (b) Cross-sectional image (90° direction)
 and (c) Images of representative interlaminar layers indicated by arrow in (a).

Thick laminates

Cross-sectional images in Fig. 8 show that there occurred matrix cracks in each layer and delaminations in each interlaminar region. Images of representative layers show that matrix cracks occurred along the fiber direction in each layer and delamination occurred with connecting matrix cracks in neighbouring layers. When the observation results of Fig. 5 was considered, it was concluded that matrix cracks and delaminations shaped the spiral stair in which the angle of neighbouring steps was 45°.

The location of an extremely large delamination in thickness direction was localized and other

Figure 9: Images of Intermediate laminates by X-ray CT:
 (a) Cross-sectional image (0° direction), (b) Cross-sectional image (90° direction)
 and (c) Images of representative interlaminar layers indicated by arrow in (a).

delaminations occurred in limited interlaminar layers in Thin laminates, while the projected damage area of Thin laminates was larger than that of Thick laminates due to the appearance of a large delamination near the mid-plane. It indicates that the ratio of the consumed energy by fiber breakages to the total energy in Thin laminates is relatively larger than that of Thick laminates.

Intermediate laminates

Fig. 9 shows that cracks including fiber breakages which perforated in several layers occurred at the back face in addition to delaminations induced by matrix cracks, indicating that Intermediate laminates showed an intermediate damage mode between Thin and Thick laminates. Focusing on the large delamination near the mid-plane, the generation mode of delamination was common to that of Thick laminates in which delamination occurred with connecting matrix cracks in neighbouring layers although the delamination propagated with long matrix cracks as observed in Thin laminates. There was no difference in the generation mode of delamination between Intermediate and Thick laminates except a large delamination near the mid-plane.

3.3 Effect of impact energy on damage mode

Fig. 10 indicates a graph in which projected delamination area is plotted as a function of impact energy. In the cases of 3 and 5 J/mm for impact energy, projected delamination area became larger when decreasing the ply thickness. These results showed the same tendency in the suppressing effect of the first ply failure such as matrix cracks and delamination by decreasing ply thickness that causes more brittle failure mode than Thick laminates, that was observed in previous static flexural tests [11].

Comparing the gradient of linear approximation for the result, the gradient was in the order of Thin, Thick and Intermediate laminates. These results indicate that the projected damage area largely depends on impact energy in Intermediate laminates. These results were attributed to the fact that Intermediate laminates exhibited an intermediate damage mode between Thin and Thick laminates. In Intermediate laminates, an extremely large delamination near the mid-plane occurred as Thin laminates in addition to the distributed delaminations in thickness direction as Thick laminates was observed. On the other hand, the accumulation of fiber breakages was suppressed in Intermediate laminates than Thin laminates, and therefore, the ratio of the consumed energy by delaminations to the total energy was higher than that of Thin laminates.

Figure 10: Projected damage area as a function of impact energy. The black line, black chain line and grey line indicate linear approximations of Thin, Intermediate and Thick laminates, respectively.

These results show the opposite tendency from those shown in Ref. [4] by Amacher et al. in which Intermediate specimens (aerial fiber weight : 100 gsm) that correspond to Intermediate laminates in this study (aerial fiber weight : 120 gsm) exhibited the smaller projected damage area than Thin and Thick specimens (aerial fiber weight : 30 and 300 gsm respectively). This difference might be attributed to the difference in fiber dispersion of the prepreg sheet. Cross-sectional image of uni-directional laminates which consisted of prepreg of which aerial fiber weight was 100 gsm in Ref. [4] showed the appearance of resin rich region. Besides, the range of fiber volume fraction of the laminates in Ref. [4] was 51.4-59.4%. It was considered that this heterogeneity could generate the resin rich region also in interlaminar layer that suppressed the propagation of delaminations. Hojo et al. [12] investigated the effect of self same resin layer on interlaminar fracture toughness of uni-directional CF/epoxy laminates. They concluded that Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness was improved by appearance of resin layer. Their conclusion can explain the results in Ref. [4]. In contrast, as shown in Fig. 1, thin-ply prepreps with a homogenous fiber dispersion were used for the preparation of all the laminates in this study in order to avoid both factors of the difference in fiber volume fraction between the laminates and the heterogeneity of fiber dispersion in each layer of laminates. As the results, there was no difference of fiber volume fraction which could cause the difference in the propagation of the delamination, and resin rich region was not generated in interlaminar layers due to the homogeneous fiber dispersion, and therefore a propagation of the delamination near the mid-plane was promoted as a consequence.

3.4 Load-displacement curves of the impact tests

Comparison between Thin and Thick laminates

Fig. 11 shows load-displacement curves of impact tests. Although there was no difference in the shape of the curves in the case of 3 J/mm, the difference was confirmed in the graphs of 5 and 7 J/mm. The load increased with increase of the displacement in spite of the appearance of small load drops in Thick laminates. In contrast, a remarkable load drop was observed when the displacement reached to about 3 mm, and the plateau region was continued until the maximum displacement in Thin laminates. The same results were confirmed in Ref. [10] by Garcia-Rodriguez in which the QSI tests in addition to impact tests were conducted in order to investigate the failure at an arbitrary load using quasi-isotropic laminates that had different ply thicknesses. As the results, they concluded that the failure process by an out-of-plane direction load consisted of three processes shown below, which are common when the laminates have the different ply thickness. First, tensile and shear cracks develop in the bottom part of the laminates, accompanied by a delamination in the $0^\circ/45^\circ$ interface. Then, shear cracks extend from the bottom to the top and allow delaminations propagating through the thickness direction. Finally, fiber breakages accumulate near the back face, subsequently developing towards the top and leading to further damage propagation.

Considering the results obtained in this study based on the proposed cumulative damage process, matrix cracks and delamination which would occur at the first step was suppressed by constraining effect by neighbouring layers, and therefore fiber breakage suddenly occurred without the first and

Figure 11: Load-displacement curves of impact tests when the impact energy was (a) 3 J/mm, (b) 5 J/mm and (c) 7 J/mm.

second steps in Thin laminates while delamination occurred stepwise in thickness direction in Thick laminates. It means that most of total energies accumulated without consumed by matrix cracks and delamination owing to suppressing effect of first ply failure were drastically consumed in Thin laminates in which bending stiffness was maintained.

This difference in load-displacement curves between Thin and Thick laminates obviously indicates the difference in cumulative damage process between them. Yokozeki et al. [13] conducted QSI tests using quasi-isotropic laminates which consisted of prepreg sheets that was 0.07 and 0.14 mm, respectively, in order to confirm the effect of ply thickness on damage mode, and investigated the effect of delamination on the generation of fiber breakages by considering experimental results using a FEM model. From the results, they concluded that fiber breakages were inhibited by an appearance of delamination near the back face that reduced the tensile stress in the fiber direction near the back face. Their conclusion corresponds to the results obtained in this study.

Intermediate laminates

The fact that no sudden load drop was observed in Intermediate laminates while there was no difference in the initial gradient of the curve between Intermediate and Thin laminates indicates Intermediate laminates showed an intermediate damage mode between Thin and Thick laminates also in load-displacement curves. Cugnoni et al. [9] examined the suppressing effect of ply failure by decreasing ply thickness by considering their experimental results of tensile tests of quasi-isotropic laminates which had different ply thicknesses using in-situ model proposed by Camanho et al. [14] which could explain that matrix cracks were suppressed due to the enhancement of in-situ strength by constraining effect of neighbouring layers when decreasing ply thickness. Their results experimentally demonstrated that in-situ effect was expressed when the ply thickness was less than 134 μm . According to their results, the ply thickness of Intermediate laminates in this study (120 μm) was in the range of ply thickness in which in-situ effect was able to be expressed. In in-situ model, in-situ strength is in inverse proportion to the square root of the ply thickness. Therefore, although the degree of in-situ effect was smaller than that of Thin laminates, this slight effect in Intermediate laminates led an intermediate damage mode between Thin and Thick laminates.

Figure 12: CAI strength as a function of impact energy.

Figure 13: CAI strength as a function of projected damage area.

The black line, black chain line and grey line indicate quadratic curve approximations of Thin, Intermediate and Thick laminates, respectively.

3.5 Effect of ply thickness on CAI strength

Figs. 12 and 13 depict the results of CAI tests. Figs. 12 and 13 are the graphs in which CAI strength is plotted as a function of impact energy calculated from the measured velocity of impactor and the projected damage area obtained from ultrasonic inspection, respectively. Fig.12 indicates that CAI strength was improved by decreasing ply thickness when the impact energy was below 5 J/mm. In contrast, reduction of CAI strength in Thin laminates was confirmed when the impact energy was 7 J/mm. This reduction was caused by the fiber breakage observed in X-ray CT (Fig. 8). When the impact energy was 7 J/mm, the propagation of fiber breakages in thickness direction was promoted in Thin laminates, the ratio of intact 0° direction fibers which could bear a large load was reduced. In Intermediate laminates, although the projected damage area became larger with increase of the impact energy, the number of fiber breakage was smaller than that in Thin laminates in addition to the localization of a large delamination near the mid-plane, and therefore reduction of CAI strength was suppressed even in the case of a high impact energy.

Comparing the gradients of approximation curves in Fig. 13, Thin laminates exhibited the larger value than other laminates. These results indicate that CAI strength depends further on the accumulation of fiber breakage than the projected damage area while the opposite tendency was confirmed in Intermediate and Thick laminates due to the slight fiber breakage. Therefore, it was shown that fiber breakage was a predominant damage mode during an impact event by decreasing ply thickness, that caused a remarkable drop of CAI strength when the impact energy was high.

According to the results in this study, it was shown that the damage mode during an impact event and the CAI strength were influenced by ply thickness of the laminates and the impact energy significantly. These results show the potential of hybrid laminates using thin and thick-ply prepregs that have both features of the high CAI strength for a low impact energy observed in Thin laminates and the retention of CAI strength for a high impact energy observed in Intermediate laminates.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a precise observation of damage by an impact load inside the quasi-isotropic laminates which had different ply thicknesses using thin-ply prepreg that was 0.02 mm in thickness was conducted, and the effect of ply thickness and impact energy on the damage modes in impact tests and CAI strength was discussed. The results are summarized as below:

1. Fiber breakages became a predominant damage mode by decreasing the ply thickness due to constraining effect of neighbouring layers while the most of failures in thick-ply laminates was resin failure such as matrix cracks and delamination.
2. A brittle failure mode was confirmed during the impact test as well as in previous static load tests by decreasing ply thickness since a remarkable load drop was observed until the maximum displacement in load-displacement curves.
3. By decreasing ply thickness, the decreasing rate of CAI strength was larger than Thick laminates due to the propagation of fiber breakages in thickness direction in the case of a high impact energy, while the CAI strength was improved when the impact energy was below 5 J/mm.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the support of Innovative Composite Center (ICC) in Kanazawa Institute of Technology for use of the facility (X-ray CT).

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